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World Inventory of Beetles of the Family *Chrysomelidae* (Coleoptera). Part 1: Eastern Europe and Northern Asia. Check List from 1768 to 2004

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents list of beetles of the family *Chrysomelidae* and their occurrence. The paper includes: 8 subfamilies, 12 tribes, 93 genera, 34 subgenera and 892 species of beetles belonging to the family *Chrysomelidae*.

Keywords: *Chrysomelidae*, *Alticinae*, *Cassidinae*, *Chlamisinae*, *Clytrinae*, *Criocerinae*, *Donaciinae*, *Eumolpinae*, *Hispinae*

Subfamilies

<i>Alticinae</i>2
<i>Cassidinae</i>42
<i>Chlamisinae</i>49
<i>Clytrinae</i>49
<i>Criocerinae</i>58
<i>Donaciinae</i>60
<i>Eumolpinae</i>65
<i>Hispinae</i>72

– Check List –

Kingdom: *Animalia*

Phylum: *Arthropoda*

Class: *Hexapoda*

Order: *Coleoptera*

Family *Chrysomelidae* Latreille, 1802

Subfamily *Alticinae* Newman, 1834

Genus *Phyllotreta* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Phyllotreta acutecarinata Heikertinger, 1941

Distribution: Southern parts of Central Europe, Balkans, S Ukraine, SE European Russia

Phyllotreta andreevae Lopatin, 1992

Distribution: E Tajikistan (Badakhshan)

Phyllotreta annae Konstantinov, 1992

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Karatau Mountains)

Phyllotreta araxicola Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1968

Distribution: Armenia, Azerbaijan

Phyllotreta armoraciae (Koch, 1803)

Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Siberia, Introduced to N America

Phyllotreta astrachanica Lopatin, 1977

Distribution: Central, S and SE Europe, Transcaucasia, Turkey, NW Kazakhstan

Phyllotreta atra (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Sakhalin), Mongolia

Phyllotreta austriaca Heikertinger, 1909

Distribution: Southern parts of Central Europe, Ciscaucasia, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Amurland, western parts of Maritime Prov.), Korea

Phyllotreta bactriana Heikertinger, 1941

Distribution: Turkmenistan, S Tajikistan, SE Uzbekistan

Phyllotreta balcanica Heikertinger, 1909

Distribution: Distribution: S and southern parts of Central and E Europe, Caucasus, Daghestan, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Afghanistan

Phyllotreta banghaasi Heikertinger, 1941

Distribution: Turkmenistan, S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan

Phyllotreta bartanga Lopatin, 1966

Distribution: Tajikistan (Badakhshan)

Phyllotreta beschkentic Lopatin, 1961

Distribution: S Tajikistan

Phyllotreta brevistriata Kimoto, 1966

Distribution: S Kurile Is., Japan

Phyllotreta buchtarmensis Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: E Kazakhstan

Phyllotreta buhseae Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1978

Distribution: Turkmenistan

Phyllotreta caucasicola Heikertinger, 1941

Distribution: Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Middle East

Phyllotreta corrugata Reiche, 1858

Distribution: S Europe, Ukraine, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan

Phyllotreta cruciferae (Goeze, 1777)

Distribution: Europe except for Fennoscandia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Central Asia, India, Mongolia, N Africa, Introduced to N America

Phyllotreta curvipes Heikertinger, 1941

Distribution: S Kazakhstan

Phyllotreta dacica Heikertinger, 1941

Distribution: Balkans, S Ukraine, Transcaucasia, Turkey

Phyllotreta diademata Foudras, 1860

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Middle East, Central Asia, N India

Phyllotreta dilatata C. G. Thomson, 1866

Distribution: Central Europe, Asian Russia (Middle Siberia: Krasnoyarsk Distr.)

Phyllotreta erysimi erysimi J. Weise, 1900

Distribution: SE Europe, Ukraine, S European Russia, Caucasus, Turkey, Middle East, Central Asia, Mongolia

Phyllotreta erysimi baicalica Heikertinger, 1941

Distribution: Asian Russia (E Siberia), Mongolia

Phyllotreta erysimi iranella Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: Iran

Phyllotreta erysimi kutscherae Heikertinger, 1941

Distribution: Asian Russia (Siberia)

Phyllotreta erysimi tekensis Lopatin, 1992

Distribution: Turkmenistan

Phyllotreta exclamationis (Thunberg, 1784)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Asian Russia (S Siberia Russian Far East)

Phyllotreta ezoensis Kimoto 1993

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Kurile Is: Kunashir), Japan

Phyllotreta flexuosa (Illiger, 1794)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for E Mediterranean, Central Asia

Phyllotreta ganglbaueri Heikertinger, 1909

Distribution: Southern parts of Central Europe, Balkans, Crimea

Phyllotreta gurskii Lopatin, 1966

Distribution: Tajikistan (Badakhshan)

Phyllotreta humilis J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, NE China, Korea

Phyllotreta judaea Pic, 1901

Distribution: E Bulgaria, Transcaucasia (Armenia), Turkey, Near and Middle East

Phyllotreta koltzei J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov., Ussuri Area), Korea

Phyllotreta konevi Lopatin, 1985

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Isle Barsakeljmes in Aral Sea)

Phyllotreta krali Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: Iran

Phyllotreta lativittata Kutschera, 1860

Distribution: NE Mediterranean, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Near and Middle East, Central Asia, China (Sinkiang)

Phyllotreta lopatini Konstantinov, 1992

Distribution: Azerbaijan

Phyllotreta lubischevi Lopatin, 1992

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Phyllotreta maculosa Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1968

Distribution: Armenia

Phyllotreta misella Jacobson, 1901

Distribution: Asian Russia (Middle Siberia, Transbaikalia), Mongolia, N China

Phyllotreta mollis Konstantinov, 1992

Distribution: Uzbekistan

Phyllotreta mongolica L. Medvedev, 1980

Distribution: Mongolia

Phyllotreta nemorum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Central Asia, Asian Russia (S Siberia to Amurland), Mongolia, Korea, Introduced to Australia

Phyllotreta nigripes (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Near and Middle East, Central Asia, N Africa

Phyllotreta nodicornis (Marsham, 1802)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, N India

Phyllotreta ochripes (Curtis, 1837)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Iran Asian Russia (S Siberia to Far East)

Phyllotreta ogloblini Shapiro, 1960

Distribution: S Ukraine

Phyllotreta pallidipennis Reitter, 1891

Distribution: S Ukraine, SE European Russia, Ciscaucasia, Daghestan, Turkey, Central Asia, Afghanistan, Iran, Asian Russia (SW Siberia, Altai, Baikal Area, Transbaikalia), Mongolia NE China

Phyllotreta paradoxa Lopatin, 1956

Distribution: Tajikistan, Afghanistan

Phyllotreta parfentjevi Shapiro, 1958

Distribution: Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan

Phyllotreta praticola J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: SE European Russia, S Ural, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Afghanistan, Iran, Central Asia, Asian Russia (Altai), Mongolia, NW China, India

Phyllotreta procera (L. Redtenbacher, 1849)

Distribution: S and southern part of Central Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, N and NE Africa

Phyllotreta pseudoexclamationis Konstantinov, 1992

Distribution: Georgia

Phyllotreta punctulata (Marsham, 1802)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Near East, Turkey, Introduced to N America

Phyllotreta rectilineata Chen, 1939

Distribution: Asian Russia (Ussuri Area), China, Korea, Laos, N Vietnam, Japan

Phyllotreta reitteri Heikertinger, 1911

Distribution: S Ukraine (Crimea), Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan

Phyllotreta sachalinensis L. Medvedev, 1973

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Sakhalin)

Phyllotreta scheuchi Heikertinger, 1941

Distribution: England, Spain, southern parts of Central Europe, S Ukraine, Mongolia

Phyllotreta sisymbrii J. Weise, 1888

Distribution, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Iran

Phyllotreta striolata (Fabricius, 1803)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Syria, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Siberia, Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Mongolia, China, Korea, Japan, Taiwan, SE Asia, India, Indonesia, Introduced to S Africa and N America

Phyllotreta talassicola Heikertinger, 1944

Distribution: Central Asia, Afghanistan

Phyllotreta tetrastigma (Comolli, 1837)

Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (W and Middle Siberia)

Phyllotreta tomboi Lopatin, 1967

Distribution: Mongolia

Phyllotreta absunurica L. Medvedev, 1980

Distribution: Mongolia

Phyllotreta undulata Kutschera, 1860

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Central Asia, Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia, Introduced to N America

Phyllotreta ustulata Lopatin, 1961

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan

Phyllotreta vittula (L. Redtenbacher, 1849)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Central Asia, Afghanistan, Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia, Korea, China

Phyllotreta wiseana Jacobson, 1901

Distribution: S Ukraine, Crimea, SE European Russia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, N Iran, W Kazakhstan

Phyllotreta zimmermanni (Crotch, 1873)

Distribution: N Europe, Asian Russia (Middle and E Siberia, Russian Far East, N Cispacific Land), N America

Genus ***Aphthona*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Aphthona abdominalis (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Afghanistan, Iran, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia), China, Vietnam, Japan

Aphthona aeneomicans Allard, 1875

Distribution: S Europe east to Slovakia

Aphthona atrocaerulea (Stephens, 1832)

Distribution: Europe except for European Russia

Aphthona atrovirens (Forster, 1849)

Distribution: W and Central Europe, Ukraine, N Caucasus, Turkey

Aphthona beckeri Jacobson, 1896

Distribution: Southern E. Europe, Caucasus, W Kazakhstan, Siberia, Mongolia

Aphthona chalhica L. Medvedev, 1980

Distribution: Mongolia

Aphthona chekanovskii Konstantinov, 1998

Distribution: Asian Russia (Yakutia)

Aphthona chrysomelina Heikertinger, 1944

Distribution: Uzbekistan, SW Kyrgyzstan, (Chatkal Mountain Range)

Aphthona crassicornis Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: Turkey

Aphthona cyparissiae (Koch, 1803)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, W Kazakhstan

Aphthona czwalinae J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: Europe except for N, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Tuva), Mongolia

Aphthona erichsoni (Zettersterdt, 1838)

Distribution: N Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians, Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East, Kamchatka), Mongolia

Aphthona euphorbiae (Schrank, 1781)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Siberia

Aphthona flava Guillebeau, 1894

Distribution: S and SE Europe, Turkey

Aphthona flaviceps Allard, 1859

Distribution: S and SE Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Middle East, Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Aphthona franzi Heikertinger, 1944

Distribution: Southern parts of Central and SE Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Asian Russia (Altai)

Aphthona gracilipes Ogloblin, 1926

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, NW Kyrgyzstan

Aphthona gracilis Faldermann, 1837

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, NW Kyrgyzstan (Moldavia, Romania, S Ukraine, Crimea), Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, S Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Asian Russia (Transbaikalia), Mongolia

Aphthona hammarstroemi Jacobson, 1901

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Asian Russia (S Siberia east to Transbaikalia)

Aphthona hauseri Heikertinger, 1911

Distribution: Afghanistan, Iran, Central Asia

Aphthona herbigrada (Curtis, 1837)

Distribution: Europe except for N, N Africa

Aphthona hissarica Lopatin, 1975

Distribution: Iran, NE Afghanistan, Tajikistan, India (Kashmir)

Aphthona interstitialis J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Ussuri Area, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, W China, Tibet, Tajikistan

Aphthona jacobsoni Ogloblin, 1926

Distribution: Afghanistan, N Iran, Central Asia

Aphthona jakuta Ogloblin, 1926

Distribution: Asian Russia (Evenkia, Yakutia, Middle and upper Lena Valley, Cisbaikalia, Transbaikalia, Magadan Distr., Russian Far East), Mongolia

Aphthona kaszabi Kral, 1967

Distribution: Mongolia

Aphthona konstantinovi Lopatin in Konstantinov, 1998

Distribution: Crimea, N Caucasus, Turkey

Aphthona kuntzei Roubal, 1931

Distribution: E Mediterranean, Balkans, Ukraine, Turkey, Near East

Aphthona lacertosa (Rosenhauer, 1847)

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, Turkey, introduced to N America

Aphthona lopatini Konstantinov, 1998

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan

Aphthona lubischevi Konstantinov, 1998

Distribution: Crimea

Aphthona lutescens (Gyllenhal, 1813)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Transbaikalia), Mongolia, N Africa

Aphthona maculata Allard, 1876

Distribution: Caucasus, Turkey, Near East, Iran, Kazakhstan, S Tajikistan

Aphthona modesta J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), NE China, Korea

Aphthona mohri Warchałowski, 1973

Distribution: Turkmenistan, Iran

Aphthona nigriceps (W. Redtenbacher, 1842)

Distribution: S and SE Europe, S Urals, Caucasus, Turkey, Near East, N Africa

Aphthona nigriscutis Foudras, 1860

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran, W Kazakhstan, Introduced to N America

Aphthona nonstriata (Goeze, 1777)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (W Siberia)

Aphthona ovata Foudras, 1860

Distribution: S, Central and SE Europe, Transcaucasia, Turkey

Aphthona pallida (Bach, 1856)

Distribution: SE and Central Europe, Crimea, Caucasus

Aphthona perminuta Bale, 1875

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sakhalin, Kuril Is.), Korea, Japan

Aphthona placida (Kutschera, 1861)

Distribution: Central and SE Europe

Aphthona promissa Ogloblin, 1926

Distribution: Afghanistan, S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan

Aphthona przhevalskii Konstantinov, 1998

Distribution: S Kazakhstan

Aphthona pygmaea (Kutschera, 1861)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey, Near East, N Africa

Aphthona reinecki Lopatin, 1962

Distribution: NE Afghanistan

Aphthona reitteri Allard, 1884

Distribution: Caucasus, Transcaucasia

Aphthona rugipennis Ogloblin, 1926

Distribution: Caucasus, S Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan

Aphthona russica Konstantinov, Volkovitsh et Cristofaro, 2001
Distribution: W Ciscaucasia (Taman Peninsula)

Aphthona sajanica Ogloblin, 1926
Distribution: Asian Russia (Sayan, Evenkia), Mongolia, NE China

Aphthona sarmatica Ogloblin in Gavrilenko, 1928
Distribution: Southern E Europe, Crimea, Transcaucasia

Aphthona semicyanea Allard, 1859
Distribution: Central, S and SE Europe, N Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (S Siberia), Mongolia, India

Aphthona semiviridis Jacoby, 1885
Distribution: Asian Russia (S Sakhalin), Japan

Aphthona stussineri J. Weise, 1888
Distribution: Central and S Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians

Aphthona testaceicornis J. Weise, 1894
Distribution: Caucasus

Aphthona tolli Ogloblin, 1926
Distribution: N Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Yakutia, Amurland), Mongolia, China

Aphthona trivialis J. Weise, 1887
Distribution: Asian Russia (Yakutia, Ussuri Area, Amurland), N Korea

Aphthona valachica Heikertinger, 1944
Distribution: Romania, Turkey

Aphthona venustula (Kutschera, 1861)
Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey, Middle East

Aphthona violacea (Koch, 1803)
Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey, Kazakhstan, S Siberia

Aphthona wiseana Konstantinov, 1998
Distribution: Iran, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan

Genus *Longitarsus* Latreille, 1829

Subgenus *Longitarsus (Longitarsus)* Latreille, 1829

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) absynthii Kutschera, 1862

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme N, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Mongolia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) acuticollis Lopatin, 1976

Distribution: S Kazakhstan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) aeneicollis (Faldermann, 1837)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) aeruginosus (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: W and S Europe, N Mediterranean

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) albineus (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: Southern Central Europe, Balkans, N Mediterranean, Caucasus, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) alfierii alfierii Pic, 1923

Distribution: NE Mediterranean, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Kyrgyzstan, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) alfierii furthi Gruev, 1982

Distribution: N Mediterranean, Balkans, Crimea, Caucasus (Georgia)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) anatolicus J. Weise, 1900

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) aphthonoides J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: Asian Russia (Middle Siberia, Cisbaikalia, Transbaikalia, E Siberia, Amurland, Maritime Prov. Sakhalin)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) apicalis (Beck, 1817)

Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Middle Siberia, Sayan, Cisbaikalia, Transbaikalia)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) afghanicus Lopatin, 1963

Distribution: Afghanistan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) asperifoliarum J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: Caucasus, S and E Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Afghanistan, Asian Russia (Altai)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) atricillus (Linnaeus, 1761)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N, Transcaucasia, Middle East, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) ballotae (Marsham, 1802)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Ciscaucasia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, S Kazakhstan, Mongolia, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) bertii Leonardi, 1973

Distribution: Southern parts of Central Europe, Balkans, SW Ukraine, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) brisouti Heikertinger, 1912

Distribution: W and S Europe, Ukraine, Ciscaucasia, Turkey

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) brunneus (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia. SE Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Asian Russia (W and Middle Siberia, Cisbaikalia, Transbaikalia, Amurland, Russian Far East), Korea

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) callidus Warchałowski, 1967

Distribution: W and Central Europe, Transcaucasia, Iran, Kazakhstan, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) celticus Leonardi, 1975

Distribution: Southern parts of Central Europe, Ukraine

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) cerinthes (Schrank, 1798)

Distribution: Europe except N, Mediterranean, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) corpulentus J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) curtus (Allard, 1860)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Asian Russia (Transbaikalia), Afghanistan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) desertorum Heikertinger, 1913

Distribution: Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Afghanistan, Central Asia, Mongolia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) dlabolai Kral, 1964

Distribution: Caucasus (Georgia)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) echii (Koch, 1803)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Turkey, Afghanistan, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) eminus Warchałowski, 1967

Distribution: Near and Middle East, Kazakhstan, Afghanistan, Central Asia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) exsoletus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Turkmenistan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) fallax J. Weise, 1888

Distribution: S and SE Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) ferrugineus (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: Europe except for N, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) finitimus Konstantinov, 1992

Distribution: Kazakhstan (W Tian-Shan)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) foudrasi J. Weise, 1893

Distribution: Europe except N, Ciscaucasia, W Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Asian Russia (Amurland), N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) fulgens (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: Europe except for N and S, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, S Siberia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) ganglbaueri Heikertinger, 1912

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Ussuri Area, Sakhalin), Mongolia, Introduced to N America

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) georgianus (Allard, 1866)

Distribution: Caucasus (Georgia)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) godmani (Baly, 1876)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland), Korea, China, N Vietnam

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) gracilis Kutschera, 1864

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus (Arax Valley), Israel, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) hissaricus Lopatin in Konstantinov et Lopatin, 2000

Distribution: Tajikistan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) hoberlandti Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: Turkmenistan N Iran, Tajikistan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) holsaticus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asian Russia (All over Siberia), China, Korea, Japan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) indigonaceus Lopatin, 1963

Distribution: NE Afghanistan, Pakistan, India (Bengal)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) jacobaeae (Waterhouse, 1858)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Tibet, Asian Russia (All over Siberia except for N)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) jailensis Heikertinger, 1913

Distribution: Balkans, Crimea, Turkey

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) juncicola (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: W and Central Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) karlheinzi Warchałowski, 1972

Distribution: Crimea, Turkey, Near and Middle East

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) khnzoriani Palij, 1970

Distribution: W Caucasus, Kyrgyzstan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) kutscherae (Rye, 1872)

Distribution: Europe except for N and E, Ciscaucasia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Asian Russia (S Siberia), N China, Korea, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) languidus F. Kutschera, 1863

Distribution: Southern parts of Central Europe east to Transcarpathia, Caucasus

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) lateripunctatus lateripunctatus (Rosenhauer, 1856)

Distribution: Mediterranean, Near East, Caucasus

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) lateripunctatus personatus J. Weise, 1893

Distribution: Central Europe east to Ukraine, Ciscaucasia, Caucasus, Turkey, Near East

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) ledouxi Doguet, 1979

Distribution: Ciscaucasia, W Caucasus, Turkey

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) lewisii (Baly, 1874)

Distribution: Europe except for N east to Ukraine, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran, Afghanistan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Asian Russia (Siberia, Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Mongolia, NE and E China, Korea, Japan, Taiwan, N Vietnam

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) linnaei (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: Southern parts of Central, S and SE Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) longipennis Kutschera, 1863

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (S Siberia east to Tuva and Yakutia)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) longiseta J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: Europe except for S and extreme N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Asian Russia (E Siberia, Maritime Prov.), NE China, Korea, Japan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) luridus (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for Central Asia and Russian Far East, Introduced to N America

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) lycopi (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East, Iran, S Kazakhstan, Central Asia, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) marguzoricus Konstantinov in Konstantinov et Lopatin, 2000

Distribution: Central Asia (Tajikistan)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) medvedevi Shapiro, 1956

Distribution: Central, SE and E Europe, Uzbekistan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) melanocephalus (DeGeer, 1775)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, S Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (W and Middle Siberia, Transbaikalia), Mongolia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) melanoxanthus Lopatin, 1963

Distribution: S Afghanistan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) membranaceus (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) minimus Kutschera, 1863

Distribution: Southern parts of Central Europe, N Caucasus, Asian Russia (S Siberia)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) minusculus (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: Europe except for N, E Caucasus, Turkey

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) monticola Kutschera, 1863

Distribution: Mountains of W and Central Europe, Southern parts of European Russia, Caucasus, Tajikistan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) muchei Mohr, 1984

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Alai Mountain Range)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) murteus Warchałowski, 1972

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, N Afghanistan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) nanus (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: Europe except for N, E Caucasus, Near East, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) nasturtii (Fabricius, 1792)

Distribution: Europe except for N, E Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Asian Russia (All over Siberia to Russian Far East), Mongolia, NE China, Tibet

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) niger (Koch, 1803)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) nigerrimus (Gyllenhal, 1827)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Asian Russia (Amurland)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) nigrofasciatus (Goeze, 1777)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N, E Caucasus, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Afghanistan, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (W Siberia)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) nitidamiculus Kimoto, 1965

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov. Ussuri Area, Kurile Is.), Korea, Japan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) nitidus Jacoby, 1885

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov., Ussuri Area), NE China, Korea, Japan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) noricus Leonardi, 1976

Distribution: Southern parts of Central Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) oblitteratoides Gruev, 1973

Distribution: W and S Europe, Transcaucasia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) oblitteratus (Rosenhauer, 1847)

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) ochroleucus (Marsham, 1802)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, N Africa, Canary Isles

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) pallidicornis Kutschera, 1863

Distribution: Mountains of W, Central and E Europe

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) parvulus (Paykull, 1799)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East, Asian Russia (W and Middle Siberia, Sayan, Cisbaikalia), N Africa, Canary Isles, Madeira

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) pellucidus (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Mongolia, N Africa, Introduced to N America

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) picicollis (J. Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Bulgaria, Romania and Ukraine, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Middle East, Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) pratensis (Panzer, 1794)

Distribution: Europe Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, N Africa, Canary Isles, Introduced to N America

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) pulmonoriae J. Weise, 1893

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, Caucasus

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) quadriguttatus (Pontoppidan, 1765)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Ciscaucasia, E Caucasus, Turkey

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) ratshensis Khnzorian, 1962

Distribution: Caucasus (Georgia)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) rectilineatus (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: W, S and southern parts of Central Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Afghanistan, Kazakhstan, N Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) reichei (Allard, 1860)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Iran

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) rubellus (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: Mountains of Central and E Europe

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) rubiginosus (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: All over Palaeartic except for SW and E Mediterranean, and N Africa. Introduced to N America

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) sahlbergi Pic, 1907

Distribution: S Kazakhstan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) salarius Lopatin et Kulenova, 1985

Distribution: Kazakhstan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) salviae Gruev, 1975

Distribution: Europe except for N and E, Crimea, Caucasus, Transcaucasia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) scutellaris (Rey, 1874)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Mongolia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) silbursaicus Lopatin, 2004

Distribution: Tajikistan (S Slopes of Hissar Mountain Range)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) strigicollis Wollaston, 1864

Distribution: S and southern parts of Central Europe, Caucasus (Georgia), N Africa, Canary Isles

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) substriatus Kutschera, 1863

Distribution: W, S, SE and southern parts of Central Europe, N Caucasus, Kazakhstan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) succineus (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: All over Palaeartic, Introduced to N America

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) suturatus (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: W and S Mediterranean, Crimea, N Caucasus

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) suturellus (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: All over Palaeartic except for Mediterranean, Transcaucasia, Central Asia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) symphyti Heikertinger, 1912

Distribution: Europe except for N and S, W Caucasus, Uzbekistan Asian Russia (Tuva)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) tabidus (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan Mongolia, N, Africa

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) tienshanicus Konstantinov, 1992

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Ugam Mountain Range)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) tishechkini Konstantinov, 2000

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Zaili Alatau)

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) tournafortiae L. Medvedev et Voronova, 1979

Distribution: Mongolia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) transbaicalicus Ogloblin, 1917

Distribution: S and Asian Russia (Middle Siberia, Cisbaikalia, Transbaikalia, Amurland), Mongolia

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) trepidus Warchałowski, 1973

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey, Middle East

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) tristis J. Weise, 1888

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, E Caucasus

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) tshikatunovi Lopatin, 1966

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan

Longitarsus (Longitarsus) violentoides Konstantinov, 2000

Distribution: Armenia (Tsahkadzor)

***Longitarsus (Longitarsus) violentus* J. Weise, 1893**

Distribution: SE European Russia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Middle East, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (S and Middle Siberia, Transbaikalia, Tuva, Yakutia, Beringia), Mongolia

Subgenus ***Longitarsus (Testergus)* J. Weise, 1893**

***Longitarsus (Testergus) anchusae* (Paykull, 1799)**

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Asian Russia (Altai, Transbaikalia)

***Longitarsus (Testergus) anatolicus* J. Weise, 1900**

Distribution: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan

***Longitarsus (Testergus) brachypterus* J. Weise, 1890**

Distribution: Caucasus (Arax Valley)

***Longitarsus (Testergus) ellipticus* Reitter, 1909**

Distribution: S Kazakhstan

***Longitarsus (Testergus) excisipennis* Lopatin, 1967**

Distribution: S Tajikistan

***Longitarsus (Testergus) fuscoaeneus* L. Redtenbacher, 1849**

Distribution: Europe except for N, Crimea, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East

***Longitarsus (Testergus) hittita* Biondi, 1995**

Distribution: Armenia, Turkey

***Longitarsus (Testergus) imitator* Lopatin, 1967**

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Central Asia

***Longitarsus (Testergus) josiphi* Konstantinov, 1994**

Distribution: Kazakhstan (W Tian-Shan)

***Longitarsus (Testergus) lederi* J. Weise, 1889**

Distribution: Ciscaucasia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia

***Longitarsus (Testergus) mohri* Lopatin, 1963**

Distribution: S Afghanistan

***Longitarsus (Testergus) pinguis* J. Weise, 1888**

Distribution: SE and southern parts of Central Europe, Turkey, Syria

***Longitarsus (Testergus) primaeveris* Lopatin, 1967**

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, S Kyrgyzstan, SW Tajikistan, S Uzbekistan

Longitarsus (Testergus) pubescens J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: Caucasus (Abkhazia, Georgia, Armenia)

Longitarsus (Testergus) radiatus Konstantinov, 1992

Distribution: Uzbekistan (W Tian-Shan)

Longitarsus (Testergus) sengloki Konstantinov, 1994

Distribution: Tajikistan (Senglok Mountain Range)

Longitarsus (Testergus) sogdianus Lopatin, 1956

Distribution: Tajikistan (South of Hissar Mountain Range)

Longitarsus (Testergus) tmetopterus Jacobson, 1893

Distribution: S Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Afghanistan

Longitarsus (Testergus) turcomanorum Lopatin, 1967

Distribution: S Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan

Longitarsus (Testergus) weisei Guillebeau, 1895

Distribution: W Europe, Albania, Poland, Turkey, Middle East, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Nepal, China

Genus ***Hermaeophaga*** Foudras, 1860

Hermaeophaga mercurialis (Fabricius, 1792)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey

Hermaeophaga nigricornis Ogloblin, 1921

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Dauria)

Hermaeophaga ruficollis (H. Lucas, 1849)

Distribution: Central Asia, India (Mysore), Sri Lanka, N and W Africa

Genus ***Altica*** Geoffroy, 1762

Altica aenescens (J. Weise, 1888)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N and S

Altica ancyrensis (J. Weise, 1897)

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East

Altica balassogloi (Jacobson, 1892)

Distribution: Afghanistan, Pakistan Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia

Altica bicarinata (Kutschera, 1860)

Distribution: E Medinerranean, Turkey, Iran,

Altica bisulcata (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Mongolia, Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.)

Altica brevicollis Foudras, 1860

Distribution: Europe except for extreme S and N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran
Kazakhstan

Altica breviuscula (J. Weise, 1900)

Distribution: Azerbaijan, Iran

Altica carduorum Guerin-Meneville, 1858

Distribution: Europe except for the N, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan,
Tajikistan, introduced to N America

Altica carinthiaca (J. Weise, 1888)

Distribution: N, NW and Mountains of Central Europe, Transcaucasia, Kyrgyzstan,
Uzbekistan, Asian Russia (N Baikal)

Altica chamaenerii (Lindberg, 1926)

Distribution: N and Mountains of Central Europe, Transcaucasia, Kyrgyzstan, Asian
Russia (Beringia, Kamchatka)

Altica circaeae Ohno, 1960

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Kurile Is.), Japan

Altica cornivorax Kral, 1969

Distribution: Southern parts of Central Europe, Ukraine, Turkey

Altica deserticola (J. Weise, 1889)

Distribution: SE European Russia, S Urals, SW Kazakhstan, W Caspian Plain, Ciscaucasia,
Transcaucasia, Near East, Turkey, Afghanistan, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, N
and NW China, Mongolia, Taiwan

Altica difficilis (Ogloblin, 1921)

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Altica engstroemi (J. Sahlberg, 1894)

Distribution: N Europe, SE Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W and Middle Siberia, Altais,
Transbaikalia, Chukotka, Kamchatka)

Altica fragariae (Nakane, 1955)

Distribution: E and NE China, Korea, Asian Russia (Sakhalin), Japan

Altica fruticola (J. Weise, 1888)

Distribution: Central Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians

Altica globicollis (J. Weise, 1889)

Distribution: SW Caucasus, Transcaucasia, NW Iran, Turkey

Altica hampei (Allard, 1867)

Distribution: Crimea, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey

Altica helianthemi (Allard, 1859)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Tuva, Transbaikalia, Yakutia)

Altica impressicollis (Reiche, 1862)

Distribution: Central, S and SE Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Near and Middle East

Altica ivlievi (L. Medvedev, 1968)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Magadan Distr.)

Altica jarmilae Kral, 1979

Distribution: E Mediterranean, Turkey, Caucasus (Georgia)

Altica kozlovi (Ogloblin, 1921)

Distribution: N China

Altica longicollis (Allard, 1860)

Distribution: Europe except for S

Altica lubischevi (Palič, 1963)

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, China (Tibet)

Altica lythri Aube, 1843

Distribution: Europe except for N

Altica mohri Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: E Iran

Altica nuristanica (Lopatin, 1963)

Distribution: E and NE Afghanistan

Altica oleracea (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic, except for extreme N

Altica opacifrons (H. Lindberg, 1938)

Distribution: N Europe

Altica palustris (J. Weise, 1888)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Middle East, Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Altica pamiranica (J. Weise, 1889)

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, NW China

Altica plotnicovi (Palij, 1963)

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Altica pontica (Ogloblin, 1925)

Distribution: Turkey

Altica quercetorum quercetorum Foudras, 1860

Distribution: Central and S Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey

Altica quercetorum saliceti (J. Weise, 1888)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N, Armenia

Altica rosicola Kral, 1969

Distribution: W Caucasus, Armenia

Altica sajanica (Csiki, 1901)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Middle Siberia, Transbaikalia, Amurland)

Altica semenovi (Jacobson, 1892)

Distribution: Central Asia, NW China

Altica sibirica (Csiki, 1901)

Distribution: Asian Russia (W Siberia)

Altica stichai Kral, 1965

Distribution: W Caucasus, Transcaucasia

Altica talassicola Lopatin, 1976

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan

Altica talyshana Konstantinov, 1995

Distribution: Azerbaijan

Altica tamaricis Schrank, 1785

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Middle East, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Transbaikalia)

Altica tristis (Ogloblin, 1921)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia)

Altica tsharynensis (Ogloblin, 1921)

Distribution: Kazakhstan

Altica viridula (J. Weise, 1889)

Distribution: Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Iran

Altica weisei (Jacobson, 1892)

Distribution: Asian Russia (NE and E Siberia), Korea, N China

Genus *Batophila* Foudras, 1860

Batophila acutangula Hikertinger, 1921

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Ussuri Area, Maritime Prov. Sakhalin), Korea, N China, Taiwan

Batophila dogueti Doberl, 1894

Distribution: Azerbaijan, Iran

Batophila fallax J. Weise, 1888

Distribution: Southern Central and SE Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran

Batophila olexai Kral, 1964

Distribution: Balkans, Transcaucasia, Turkey

Batophila rubi (Paykull, 1799)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus

Genus *Mniophila* Stephens, 1832

Mniophila muscorum muscorum (Koch, 1803)

Distribution: Europe except for SW and NE, Caucasus, Transcaucasia

Genus *Lythraria* Bedel, 1897

Lythraria salicariae (Paykull, 1800)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for E Mediterranean, N Africa and Central Asia

Genus *Ochrosis* Foudras, 1860

Ochrosis ventralis (Illiger, 1807)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey, Near and Middle East, N Africa, Canary Isles, Madeira

Genus *Neocrepidodera* Heikertinger, 1911

Neocrepidodera brevicollis (J. Daniel, 1904)

Distribution: Mountains of W Central and E Europe

Neocrepidodera corpulenta (Kutschera, 1860)

Distribution: Mountains of W, Central E and SE Europe

Neocrepidodera crassicornis crassicornis (Faldermann, 1837)

Distribution: S and SE Europe, Ciscaucasia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Kazakhstan

Neocrepidodera cyanescens cyanescens (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: Mountains of W and Central Europe

Neocrepidodera femorata (Gyllenhal, 1813)

Distribution: Mountains of W, Central and E Europe, N Europe, Asian Russia (W and Middle Siberia, Altai, Baikal Area, Tuva)

Neocrepidodera ferruginea (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran

Neocrepidodera impressa impressa (Fabricius, 1801)

Distribution: S Europe, Near East, N Africa

Neocrepidodera interpunctata (Motschulsky, 1859)

Distribution: N Europe, Middle Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Tuva, Baikal Area, Transbaikalia, Yakutia, Amurland, Maritime Prov., Ussuri Area, Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Mongolia, China, Korea, Japan

Neocrepidodera kozhantshikovi (Jacobson, 1925)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Yakutia)

Neocrepidodera melanostoma (L. Redtenbacher, 1849)

Distribution: Mountains of W, Central and E Europe

Neocrepidodera motschulskii (Konstantinov, 1991)

Distribution: Europe except for S, Caucasus

Neocrepidodera nigrifula (Gyllenhal, 1813)

Distirbution: Europe except for SW

Neocrepidodera obscuritarsis (Motschulsky, 1859)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov., Ussuri Area, NE Sakhalin), China, Japan

Neocrepidodera puncticollis (Reitter, 1879)

Distribution: Carpathians

Neocrepidodera sibirica (Pic, 1909)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Ussuri Area)

Neocrepidodera sublaevis (Motschulsky, 1859)

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Afghanistan, N Tajikistan, Asian Russia (Middle and E Siberia to Russian Far East), Mongolia

Neocrepidodera transsilvanica (Fuss, 1864)

Distribution: Carpathians

Neocrepidodera transversa (Marsham, 1802)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran

Genus ***Orestia*** Germar, 1845

Orestia aubei Allard, 1859

Distribution: Mountains of Central, E and northern parts of SE Europe, (Dinaric Mts., Carpathians)

Orestia carpathica Reitter, 1880

Distribution: Mountains of Central Europe (Czerna Gora, Carpathians)

Orestia caucasica Reitter, 1879

Distribution: Ciscaucasia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia

Orestia paveli Frivaldszky, 1877

Distribution: Mountains of Central, E and northern parts of SE Europe (Dinaric Mts., Carpathians)

Genus ***Crepidodera*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1836

Crepidodera aurata (Marsham, 1802)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W, S, Middle and NE Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia, N China, Korea, N Africa

Crepidodera aurea (Geoffroy, 1785)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey, E Kazakhstan, W Siberia

Crepidodera fulvicornis (Fabricius, 1792)

Distribution: Europe, Ciscaucasia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East, N Iran, NW and E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W and Middle Siberia, Cisbaikalia, Transbaikalia, Amurland), Mongolia

Crepidodera japonica Baly, 1877

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Japan

Crepidodera lamina (Bedel, 1901)

Distribution: Europe except of N, NW Caucasus

Crepidodera nigricoxis Allard, 1878

Distribution: Southern parts of Central Europe, SE Europe east to Rumania, Caucasus, N Korea

Crepidodera nitidula (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for SW, Asian Russia (W and Middle Siberia, Sayan)

Crepidodera obscuripes (Heikertinger, 1912)

Distribution: Asian Russia (E Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia, China, Korea

Crepidodera picipes (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Cisbaikalia, Transbaikalia, Ussuri Area, Amurland, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), N China, Korea

Crepidodera plutus (Latreille, 1804)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Asian Russia (Siberia to Russian Far East, Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Mongolia, N, China, Korea, Japan

Crepidodera sahalinensis Konstantinov, 1996

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sakhalin, Kunashir Isle)

Crepidodera ussuriensis Konstantinov, 1996

Distribution: Asian Russia (Russian Far East)

Crepidodera viridis Gressitt et Kimoto, 1963

Distribution: Asian Russia (Russian Far East), NW China

Genus ***Derocrepis*** J. Weise, 1886

Derocrepis pubipennis Reitter, 1892

Distribution: Armenia, Georgia, Transcaucasia

Derocrepis rufipes (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for N and Mediterranean, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Asian Russia (W and Middle Siberia, Sayan)

Derocrepis serbica caucasica J. Weise, 1886

Distribution: Caucasus

Derocrepis serbica jajlensis Heikertinger, 1922

Distribution: Crimea

Derocrepis serbica laterufa Pic, 1909
Distribution: N Caucasus, Georgia

Derocrepis serbica ossetica Heikertinger, 1922
Distribution: Caucasus (N Ossetia)

Derocrepis serbica serbica (Kutschera, 1860)
Distribution: Balkans, Crimea

Genus ***Novofoudrasia*** Jacobson, 1901

Novofoudrasia rufiventris (J. Weise, 1900)
Distribution: Uzbekistan, S Kazakhstan, Afghanistan, Tajikistan, Nepal

Genus ***Hippuriphila*** Foudras, 1860

Hippuriphila babai Chujo, 1959
Distribution: Asian Russia (Sakhalin, Kurile Is), Japan

Hippuriphila modeeri (Linnaeus, 1761)
Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Asian Russia (Siberia), Mongolia

Genus ***Epitrix*** Foudras, 1860

Epitrix abeillei (Bauduer, 1874)
Distribution: Turkey, Middle and Near East, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, NE China, Mongolia, N Africa

Epitrix atropae Foudras, 1860
Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, N Africa

Epitrix caucasica (Heikertinger, 1950)
Distribution: S European Russia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, India (Himalaya)

Epitrix dieckmanni (Mohr, 1968)
Distribution: Turkmenistan, Near and Middle East, Saudi Arabia

Epitrix ermischii (Mohr, 1968)
Distribution: Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Iran

Epitrix intermedia Foudras, 1860
Distribution: Southern parts of Central Europe, Balkans, Ukraine, Caucasus, Turkey

Epitrix ogloblini (Iablokoff-Khuzorian, 1960)

Distribution: Armenia

Epitrix pubescens (Koch, 1803)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia), Azores Isles

Epitrix wuorentausi (Heikertinger, 1950)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Ussuri Area, Maritime Prov.)

Genus *Minota* Kutschera, 1859

Minota carpathica Heikertinger, 1911

Distribution: Mountains of W, Central, E and SE Europe

Genus *Apteropeda* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Apteropeda globosa (Illiger, 1794)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N

Apteropeda orbiculata (Marsham, 1802)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N and E

Apteropeda splendida Allard, 1860

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N and E

Genus *Podagrica* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Podagrica fuscicornis (Linnaeus, 1766)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East, N Africa

Podagrica malvae (Illiger, 1807)

Distribution: S and southern parts of Central and E Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East

Podagrica menetriesi (Faldermann, 1837)

Distribution: S and SE Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Genus *Chaetocnema* Stephens, 1832

Chaetocnema aerosa (Letzner, 1846)

Distribution: Europe except for S and SE, Caucasus, Daghestan, Turkey, Israel

Chaetocnema arenacea (Allard, 1860)

Distribution: S and SE Europe, Caucasus, Daghestan, Turkey, N Africa

Chaetocnema arida (Foudras, 1860)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, N Africa

Chaetocnema aridula (Gyllenhal, 1827)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Asian Russia (Siberia), N Africa

Chaetocnema arisi Pic, 1915

Distribution: S Kazakhstan

Chaetocnema breviuscula (Faldermann, 1837)

Distribution: S and SE Europe, Latvia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Middle East, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Asian Russia (southern parts of W Siberia), N China, Korea

Chaetocnema chlorophana (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: S, SE and southern parts of Central Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Iraq, N Africa

Chaetocnema compressa (Letzner, 1864)

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan

Chaetocnema concinna (Marsham, 1802)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Israel, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East, Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Mongolia, China, Korea, Vietnam, Taiwan, Japan, N Africa, introduced to N America

Chaetocnema concinnicollis (Baly, 1874)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Ussuri Area, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan, SE Asia

Chaetocnema conducta (Motschulsky, 1838)

Distribution: S, SE and southern parts of Central Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East, Iran, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, N, W and S Africa

Chaetocnema confusa (Boheman, 1851)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey

Chaetocnema costulata (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Afghanistan, Asian Russia (Cisbaikalia, Sayan, Transbaikalia, Buriatia, Tuva, Yakutia, Amurland, Maritime Prov., Kamchatka, Sakhalin), Mongolia, China

Chaetocnema coyeyi (Allard, 1863)

Distribution: SE Europe, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East

Chaetocnema gottwaldi Kral, 1969

Distribution: W Kazakhstan

Chaetocnema heptapotamica Lubischev, 1963

Distribution: Caucasus, SE Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan

Chaetocnema hortensis (Geoffroy, 1785)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Asian Russia (W, Middle and S Siberia, Cisbaikalia, Sayan, Cispacific Land, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), N Africa

Chaetocnema ingenua (Baly, 1876)

Distribution: Afghanistan, China, Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov. Kurile Is.), Korea

Chaetocnema jelineki Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: SE Iran

Chaetocnema kabakovi Lopatin, 1995

Distribution: Afghanistan

Chaetocnema klapperichi Lopatin, 1963

Distribution: Afghanistan

Chaetocnema laevicollis (C. G. Thomson, 1866)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, N Iran, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Tuva, Ussuri Area, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, NE China

Chaetocnema major major (Jacquelin du Val, 1852)

Distribution: S, SE and southern E Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Kazakhstan

Chaetocnema major mandschurica Heikertinger, 1951

Distribution: Asian Russia (Ussuri Area, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), NE China, Japan

Chaetocnema mannerheimii (Gyllenhal, 1827)

Distribution: Europe except for SW, Caucasus, Daghestan, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Asian Russia (W, Middle, S and NE Siberia), Mongolia

Chaetocnema medvedevi Palij, 1968

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (E Tian-Shan)

Chaetocnema montenegrina Heikertinger, 1912

Distribution: SE Europe, Turkey, Middle East, Central Asia

Chaetocnema nebulosa J. Weise, 1866

Distribution: S Ukraine, Crimea, Caucasus, Iran, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia

Chaetocnema obesa (Boieldieu, 1859)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Altai), China, Mongolia

Chaetocnema oblonga Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: S Iran

Chaetocnema ogloblini Palij, 1970

Distribution: Asian Russia (Ussuri Area, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), NE China

Chaetocnema orientalis (Bauduer, 1874)

Distribution: SE Europe east to Romania, Caucasus, Turkey, Near East, Iran, Turkmenistan

Chaetocnema procerula (Rosenhauer, 1856)

Distribution: S and SE Europe, Turkey, N Africa

Chaetocnema psylloides Pic, 1909

Distribution: Middle East, S Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Chaetocnema sahlbergii (Gyllenhal, 1827)

Distribution: Europe except Mediterranean, Caucasus, Turkey, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Cisbaikalia, Cispaik Land, Amurland, Kamchatka)

Chaetocnema scheffleri (Kutschera, 1864)

Distribution: S, Central and SE Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, N Africa

Chaetocnema schlaeflii (Stierlin, 1866)

Distribution: Caucasus, Middle East, Iran, Turkmenistan, NE China

Chaetocnema semicoerulea semicoerulea (Koch, 1803)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W and Middle Siberia, Cisbaikalia)

Chaetocnema semicoerulea transbaikalica Heikertinger, 1951

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Ussuri Area, Beringia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia

Chaetocnema shabalini Palij, 1968

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Chaetocnema sinuata J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (Transbaikalia), Mongolia, China (Kansu)

Chaetocnema sonkulica Palij, 1968

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Tian-Shan)

Chaetocnema splendens splendens (Motschulsky, 1845)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Cisbaikalia, Transbaikalia, Ussuri Area, Amurland), Mongolia, N China

Chaetocnema splendens ljudmilae Lopatin, 1961

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, S Tajikistan

Chaetocnema subcoerulea (Kutschera, 1864)

Distribution: Europe except for N and SW, Caucasus

Chaetocnema tibialis (Illiger, 1807)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Kazakhstan Central Asia, Asian Russia (Transbaikalia), Mongolia, N Africa

Chaetocnema ussuriensis Heikertinger, 1951

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Yakutia, Ussuri Area, Maritime Prov.), N China

Genus ***Mantura*** Stephens, 1832

Mantura ambigua (Kutschera, 1862)

Distribution: W and N Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians

Mantura chrysanthemii (Koch, 1803)

Distribution: Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians, Turkey, N Africa, Canary Isles, Madeira

Mantura cylindrica L. Miller, 1880

Distribution: Italy, S Croatia, S Bulgaria, Greece, Turkey, Caucasus

Mantura mathewsi (Stephens, 1834)

Distribution: W, S, and southern parts of Central Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians, Azerbaijan

Mantura mesasiatica Lopatin, 1965

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan

Mantura obtusata (Gyllenhal, 1813)

Distribution: Europe except for SW, Caucasus

Mantura rustica (Linnaeus, 1767)

Distribution: All over Palearctic except for N Africa

Genus ***Sphaeroderma*** Stephens, 1832

Sphaeroderma balyi balyi Jacoby, 1885

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.), Korea, China, Japan

Sphaeroderma fuscicorne Baly, 1864

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.), Korea China, Japan

Sphaeroderma rubidum (Graells, 1858)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey, Near East, N Africa, Madeira

Sphaeroderma testaceum (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N, Ciscaucasia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia

Sphaeroderma unicolor Kimoto, 1965

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), Japan

Genus ***Argopus*** Fischer-Waldheim, 1824

Argopus ahrensi (Germar, 1817)

Distribution: Central, E, and SE Europe, N Caucasus

Argopus bicolor Fischer-Waldheim, 1824

Distirbution: Balkans, SE Europe, Caucasus

Argopus intermedius J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: Asian Russia (Ussuri Area, Maritime Prov.)

Argopus nigritarsis (Gebler, 1823)

Distribution: Eastern Central and E Europe, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Altai, Sayan, Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, Korea, N and NE China, Japan

Argopus punctipennis punctipennis (Motschulsky, 1866)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sakhalin Kurile Is.), Japan

Argopus punctipennis substriatus J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov., Ussuri Area), N. Korea

Argopus unicolor Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov., Ussuri Area), Korea, Japan

Genus ***Pentamesa*** Harold, 1876

Pentamesa duodecimpunctata (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sayan, Altai, Baikal Area, Tuva, Yakutia, Amurland)

Pentamesa kondarensis arnoldi Lopatin, 1996

Distribution: Uzbekistan

Pentamesa kondarensis kondarensis Lopatin, 1956

Distribution: Uzbekistan, Tajikistan

Genus ***Argopistes*** Motschulsky, 1860

Argopistes biplagistus Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Ussuri Area, Khabarovsk Distr., Sakhalin), NE China, Korea, Japan

Argopistes coccinelliformis Csiki, 1940

Distribution: NE China, Japan, Taiwan, Vietnam

Argopistes udege Konstantinov, 1994

Distribution: Asian Russia (Russian Far East)

Argopistes unicolor Jacoby, 1885

Distribution: Asian Russia (Ussuri Area), Korea, Japan

Genus ***Hemipyxis*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Hemipyxis plagioderoides (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Asian Russia (E Siberia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Korea, China, Japan

Genus ***Philopona*** J. Weise, 1903

Philopona vibex (Erichson, 1834)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Ussuri Area, S Kurile Is., Kunashir Isle), Korea, China, Japan, Taiwan, N Vietnam, India

Genus ***Dibolia*** Latreille, 1929

Dibolia carpathica J. Weise, 1893

Distribution: SE Europe, S Urals, Ciscaucasia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, SE Kazakhstan

Dibolia cryptocephala (Koch, 1803)

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, S Urals, Ciscaucasia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Kazakhstan

Dibolia cynoglossi (Koch, 1803)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N, Armenia, Turkey

Dibolia depressiuscula Letzner, 1847

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East, NE Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Cisbaikalia, Transbaikalia), N Africa

Dibolia femoralis femoralis L. Redtenbacher, 1849

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey

Dibolia foerstieri Bach, 1856

Distribution: Europe except for N, Belarus, Crimea, SE European Russia, Transcaucasia

Dibolia kraalii Mohr, 1981

Distribution: Transcaucasia, N Iran

Dibolia mesasiatica Lopatin 1965

Distribution: Uzbekistan Tajikistan (Hissar Mountain Range)

Dibolia occultans (Koch, 1803)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey, Iran N Africa, Canary Isles

Dibolia phoenicia Allard, 1866

Distribution: Balkans, Hungary, Caucasus (Georgia), Turkey, Near East

Dibolia rugulosa L. Redtenbacher, 1849

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia

Dibolia schillingii (Letzner, 1847)

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, W Kazakhstan

Dibolia timida (Illiger, 1807)

Distribution: Europe except for N and northern parts of Central, N Africa

Dibolia tricolor Reitter, 1899

Distribution: Armenia, Turkey

Dibolia tshatkatica corpulenta Mohr, 1981

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Dibolia tshatkatica tshatkatica Palič, 1968

Distribution: Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan

Dibolia turkmenica Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1978

Distribution: Turkmenistan

Dibolia wisei Mohr, 1981

Distribution: Caucasus (Georgia)

Dibolia zaitzevi L. Medvedev, 1980
Distribution: NE China, Mongolia

Dibolia zangezurica Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1968
Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran

Genus *Psylliodes* Berthold, 1827

Psylliodes aeneolus Heikertinger, 1911
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

Psylliodes aereus austriacus Heikertinger, 1911
Distribution: Mountains of Central, E and SE Europe

Psylliodes affinis (Paykull, 1799)
Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia), N Africa

Psylliodes angusticollis Baly, 1874
Distribution: Asian Russia (Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), China, Japan, Korea, Taiwan, N Vietnam

Psylliodes araraticus Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1968
Distribution: Armenia

Psylliodes aristus Khnzorian, 1962
Distribution: Armenia

Psylliodes attenuatus (Koch, 1803)
Distribution: All over Palaeartic except for Near East and N Africa

Psylliodes callinotus Faldermann, 1837
Distribution: Caucasus

Psylliodes chalcomerus (Illiger, 1807)
Distribution: All over Palaeartic except for southern Central Asia

Psylliodes chrysocephalus (Linnaeus, 1758)
Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East, Iran, N Africa Azores, Madeira

Psylliodes circumdatus (W. Redtenbacher, 1842)
Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East, Iran, N Africa

Psylliodes cucullatus (Illiger, 1807)

Distribution: Europe except for E Mediterranean, N Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (All over Siberia), Mongolia, Korea, China (Kansu)

Psylliodes cupreatus (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: Europe except for N and E Mediterranean, Transcaucasia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Asian Russia (Siberia east to Buriatia), Mongolia

Psylliodes cupreus (Koch, 1803)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Transbaikalia), Mongolia

Psylliodes cyanescens J Weise, 1887

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Ussuri Area)

Psylliodes deplanatus L. Medvedev, 1962

Distribution: N Caucasus, Georgia

Psylliodes dilutellus Heikertinger, 1911

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Psylliodes dulcamarae (Koch, 1803)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia), Mongolia

Psylliodes frivaldskyi J. Weise, 1888

Distribution: Carpathians

Psylliodes hyoscyami (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for N Africa

Psylliodes illyricus Leonardi et Gruev, 1993

Distribution: SE Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians, Turkey

Psylliodes instabilis Foudras, 1860

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East, N Africa

Psylliodes isatidis Heikertinger, 1914

Distribution: Europe except for N, N and E Caucasus, turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Asian Russia (W Siberia), Mongolia

Psylliodes kasyi Lopatin, 1967

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran

Psylliodes longicollis J. Weise, 1900

Distribution: Ciscaucasia, Transcaucasia

Psylliodes luteolus (O. F. Muller, 1776)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Ciscaucasia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, N Africa

Psylliodes macellus agropyri Palij, 1961

Distribution: E European Russia (Cisvolgensis: Saratov Distr.), N Kazakhstan

Psylliodes macellus macellus (J. Weise, 1900)

Distribution: E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia from Krasnoyarsk Distr. to Buriatia and Dauria), Mongolia

Psylliodes marcidus (Illiger, 1807)

Distribution: Coastal parts of Atlantic, North Sea, Baltic Sea, Black Sea and Mediterranean countries

Psylliodes napi flavicornis J. Weise, 1883

Distribution: Mountains of Central and E Europe

Psylliodes napi napi (Fabricius, 1792)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, S Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Siberia east to Baikal and Yakutia), N Africa

Psylliodes nitidus L. Medvedev, 1973

Distribution: Asian Russia (Ussuri Area)

Psylliodes nivalis Khnzorian, 1962

Distribution: Caucasus (Georgia)

Psylliodes ozisiki Leonardi et Arnold, 1995

Distribution: Armenia, Turkey

Psylliodes pallidicornis Heikertinger, 1921

Distribution: Caucasus, Turkemenistan

Psylliodes persicus Allard, 1866

Distribution: Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Near and Middle East, Saudi Arabia, Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Psylliodes picinus (Marsham, 1802)

Distribution: Europe except for N

Psylliodes pubipennis Lopatin, 1958

Distribution: S Tajikistan

Psylliodes punctifrons Baly, 1874

Distribution: Asian Russia (SA Maritime Prov.), Korea, China, Japan, Taiwan, Indochina, Vietnam, Sumatra

Psylliodes reitteri parallelus J. Weise, 1890

Distribution: SE European Russia, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.) Mongolia, China

Psylliodes reitteri reitteri J. Weise, 1888

Distribution: Central and SE Europe

Psylliodes rhaicus Jacobsen, 1922

Distribution: S Ukraine, S European Russia, W Kazakhstan

Psylliodes rubroaeneus Heikertinger, 1916

Distribution: Ciscaucasia, Georgia

Psylliodes saulcyi Allard, 1867

Distribution: SE Ukraine, S European Russia, N Caucasus, Near and Middle East, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, N Africa

Psylliodes sophiae Heikertinger, 1914

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (S Siberia east to Baikal), N Africa

Psylliodes subaeneus Kutschera, 1867

Distribution: Mountains of Central and E Europe (Dynaric Mts., Carpathians)

Psylliodes subrugosus Jacoby, 1885

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sakhalin), China, Japan

Psylliodes testaceoconcolor Heikertinger, 1926

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Near East

Psylliodes thlaspis Foudras, 1860

Distribution: Europe except for N and northern parts of Central Europe, Caucasus

Psylliodes toelgi Heikertinger, 1914

Distribution: Mountains of Europe except for Fennoscandia

Psylliodes validus J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: Ciscaucasia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia

Psylliodes vindobonensis Heikertinger, 1914

Distribution: Mountains of Central, E and SE Europe

Psylliodes wrasei Leonardi et Arnold, 1995

Distribution: Balkans, S Ukraine, Caucasus (Georgia)

Genus *Nonarthra* Baly, 1862

Nonarthra cyaneum Baly, 1874

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Korea, Japan, China, Taiwan, Vietnam

Genus *Sangariola* Jacobson, 1922

Sangariola punctostriata (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sakhalin, Kunashir Isle), N China, Korea, Japan

Genus *Liprus* Motschulsky, 1860

Liprus punctostriatus Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.), Korea, Japan, China (Kiangsu, Kirin), Taiwan

Genus *Phygasia* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Phygasia fulvipennis (Baly, 1874)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov., Sikhote-Alin Mountains), Korea, N and NE China, Japan

Genus *Luperomorpha* J. Weise, 1887

Luperomorpha funesta (Baly, 1874)

Distribution: W China, Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), Korea, Japan

Luperomorpha klapperichi (Lopatin, 1962)

Distribution: NE Afghanistan

Luperomorpha suturalis Chen, 1938

Distribution: S Asian Russia (S Siberia, S Baikal Area, Amurland), Mongolia, NE China

Subfamily *Cassidinae* Gyllenhal, 1813

Tribe *Aspidimorphini* Hincks, 1952

Genus *Aspidimorpha* Hope, 1840

Aspidimorpha difformis (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Aspidimorpha transparipennis (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, China, Korea

Tribe *Cassidini* Hincks, 1952

Genus *Thlaspida* J. Weise, 1899

Thlaspida lewisi (Baly, 1874)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Genus *Glyphocassis* Spaeth, 1914

Glyphocassis spilota (Gorham, 1885)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Genus *Macromonycha* Spaeth, 1911

Macromonycha apicalis (Gebler, 1845)

Distribution: Transcaucasia, S Kazakhstan, Central Asia)

Genus *Chiridula* J. Weise, 1889

Chiridula semenovi J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Genus *Eremocassis* Spaeth, 1926

Eremocassis weisei (Jacobson, 1894)

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Genus *Ischyronota* J. Weise, 1891

Ischyronota conicollis (J. Weise, 1890)

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Mongolia

Ischyronota desertorum (Gebler, 1834)

Distribution: Southern parts of E Europe, E Ciscaucasia, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, NW China, Mongolia

Ischyronota elevata (Reitter, 1890)

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Iran

Ischyronota schusteri Spaeth, 1914

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, W China, Monoglia

Ischyronota spaethi Reitter, 1901

Distribution: Kazakhstan

Genus *Cassida* Linnaeus, 1758

Subgenus *Cassida (Alledoya)* Hincks, 1950

Cassida (Alledoya) seraphina hablitziae Motschulsky, 1838

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Kazakhstan (Chu-Ili Mountains)

Cassida (Alledoya) vespertina Boheman, 1862

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Subgenus *Cassida (Cassida)* Linnaeus, 1758

Cassida (Cassida) atrata Fabrucius, 1787

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, Turkey

Cassida (Cassida) aurora J. Weise, 1907

Distribution: Southerneastern parts of Central Europe, Ciscaucasia

Cassida (Cassida) berolinensis Suffrian, 1844

Distribution: SE Europe Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia, N China

Cassida (Cassida) denticollis Suffrian, 1844

Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Russian Far East)

Cassida (Cassida) fausti Spaeth, 1926

Distribution: S Ukraine, Ciscaucasia, Daghestan, Turkey

Cassida (Cassida) ferruginea Goeze, 1777

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, N, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia)

Cassida (Cassida) flaveola Thunberg, 1794

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N, S and Mediterranean, N Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia)

Cassida (Cassida) fusciorufa Motschulsky, 1866

Distribuiton: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Cassida (Cassida) inquinata Brulle, 1832

Distribution: Southern parts of E Europe, Caucasus, Turkmenistan

Cassida (Cassida) lineola Creutzer, 1799

Distribution: Central and southern parts of E Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Asian Russia (Siberia east to Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, China, Korea, Japan, Taiwan

Cassida (Cassida) mandli Spaeth, 1921

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Korea, China

Cassida (Cassida) mongolica Boheman, 1854

Distribution: Asian Russia (Cisbaikalia, Amurland), Mongolia, NE China

Cassida (Cassida) nebulosa Linnaeus, 1758

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for Mediterranean, introduced to N America

Cassida (Cassida) palaestina Reiche, 1858

Distribution: Near East, Transcaucasia, Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Cassida (Cassida) pallidicollis Boheman, 1856

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, China

Cassida (Cassida) pannonica Suffrian, 1848

Distribution: Southern parts of Central and SE Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Near East, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Asian Russia (W. Siberia)

Cassida (Cassida) panzeri J. Weise, 1907

Distribution: Central, E, and SE Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Siberia east to Russian Far East)

Cassida (Cassida) piperata Hope, 1842

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Cassida (Cassida) prasina Illiger 1798

Distribution: Europe except for N, SW and Mediterranean, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Siberia east to Russian Far East)

Cassida (Cassida) reitteri J. Weise, 1892

Distribution: Armenia

Cassida (Cassida) rubiginosa rubiginosa O. F. Muller, 1776

Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (W Siberia)

Cassida (Cassida) rubiginosa rugosopunctata Motschulsky, 1866

Distribution: E Asian Russia (E Siberia, Russian Far East, Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Mongolia

Cassida (Cassida) rufovirens Suffrian, 1844

Distribution: Central and southern parts of E Europe, Ciscaucasia, Turkey

Cassida (Cassida) sanguinolenta O. F. Muller, 1776

Distribution: Europe except for N and SW, Turkey, S Urals, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Cisbaikalia)

Cassida (Cassida) sanguinosa Suffrian, 1844

Distribution: Europe except for S and extreme N, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Cisbaikalia)

Cassida (Cassida) sareptana Kraatz, 1873

Distribution: Steppe of Ukraine and European Russia, Ciscaucasia, W Kazakhstan

Cassida (Cassida) seladonia Gyllenhal, 1827

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N and E, Ciscaucasia, W Kazakhstan

Cassida (Cassida) spaethi J. Weise, 1900

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Korea, China

Cassida (Cassida) stigmatica Suffrian, 1844

Distribution: Europe (except for N, NW, Iberian, Appenine and Balkan Peninsula), Turkey, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia), N, China

Cassida (Cassida) vibex Linnaeus, 1767

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for extreme N

Subgenus ***Cassida (Cassidulella)*** A. Strand, 1928

Cassida (Cassidulella) nobilis Linnaeus, 1758

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for extreme N and N Africa

Cassida (Cassidulella) parvula Boheman, 1854

Distribution: Eastern S and southern E Europe, Crimea, Ciscaucasia, Caucasus, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (S Siberia to Amurland), Mongolia

Cassida (Cassidulella) pusilla Wlthl, 1839

Distribution: E Mediterranean

Cassida (Cassidulella) velaris J. Weise, 1896

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Japan

Cassida (Cassidulella) vittata Villers, 1789

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Asian Russia (S Siberia east to Maritime Prov.), Japan

Subgenus *Cassida (Mionycha)* J. Weise, 1891

Cassida (Mionycha) azurea Fabricius, 1801

Distribution: Central and E Europe, S Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia), N Africa

Cassida (Mionycha) concha Solsky, 1872

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Cassida (Mionycha) margaritacea Schaller, 1783

Distribution: Europe (except for N, SW, northern and central parts of E), Caucasus, Turkey, N, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Cisbaikalia)

Cassida (Mionycha) subreticulata Suffrian, 1844

Distribution: Central, S and southern parts of E Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (Siberia east to Amurland), Mongolia

Subgenus *Cassida (Lordiconia)* Reitter, 1926

Cassida (Lordiconia) canaliculata Laicharting, 1781

Distribution: SE Europe and southern parts of E Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan

Subgenus *Cassida (Mionychella)* Spaeth, 1926 in Hincks, 1952

Cassida (Mionychella) hemisphaerica Herbst, 1799

Distribution: Europe except for extreme N, Caucasus, Turkey, N Africa

Subgenus *Cassida (Lordicassis)* Reitter, 1926

Cassida (Lordicassis) medvedevi Lopatin, 1965

Distribution: Tajikistan (Mountains)

Cassida (Lordicassis) moori Boheman, 1856

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, India (Mountains)

Cassida (Lordicassis) tianshanica Borowiec et Swietojanska, 2001

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Tian-Shan Mountains)

Cassida (Lordicassis) transcaucasica Borowiec et Swietojanska, 2001

Distribution: Transcaucasia

Cassida (Lordicassis) undecimnotata Gebler, 1834

Distribution: Middle East, Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Subgenus *Cassida (Odontionycha)* J. Weise, 1891

Cassida (Odontionycha) viridis Linnaeus, 1758

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for extreme N

Subgenus *Cassida (Onychocassis)* Spaeth in Spaeth et Reitter, 1926

Cassida (Onychocassis) bella Faldermann, 1837

Distribution: Caucasus, Turkey

Subgenus *Cassida (Taiwania)* Spaeth, 1913

Cassida (Taiwania) amurensis Kraatz, 1879

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Korea, China

Cassida (Taiwania) versicolor Boheman, 1855

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Japan

Subgenus *Cassida (Pseudocassida)* Desbrochers des Loges, 1891

Cassida (Pseudocassida) murraea Linnaeus, 1767

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for W Mediterranean, Central Asia and N Africa

Subgenus *Cassida (Tylocentra)* Reitter, 1926

Cassida (Tylocentra) saucia J. Weise 1889

Distribution: Caucasus, Turkey

Cassida (Tylocentra) sussamyrica Spaeth, 1926

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan

Cassida (Tylocentra) turcmunica J. Weise, 1892

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Mongolia

Genus *Pilemostoma* Desbrochers des Loges, 1891

Pilemostoma bucharica Spaeth, 1914

Distribution: Uzbekistan

Pilemostoma fastuosa (Schaller, 1783)

Distribution: Europe except for N and western Mediterranean, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (S. Siberia), Mongolia

Genus *Hypocassida* J. Weise, 1893

Hypocassida subferruginea (Schrank, 1776)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Afghanistan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (S Siberia east to Maritime Prov.), W China, N Africa

Subfamily *Chlamisinae* Gressitt, 1946

Genus *Chlamisus* Rafinesque, 1815

Chlamisus pubiceps (Chujo, 1940)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.), Korea

Subfamily *Clytrinae* Kirby, 1837

Tribe *Clytrini* Kirby, 1837

Genus *Labidostomis* Germar, 1822

Subgenus *Labidostomis (Labidostomis)* Germar, 1822

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) amurensis Heyden, 1884

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Khabarovsk Prov. Maritime Prov.), China, Korea

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) arcuata Pic, 1920

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, NW China

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) arnoldii L. Medvedev, 1962

Distribution: Northern Caucasus

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) asiatica Faldermann, 1837

Distribution: Transcaucasia

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) beckeri J. Weise, 1882

Distribution: S and SE parts of European Russia, Ukraine, Crimea, Moldavia, Ciscaucasia, E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia)

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) bipunctata bipunctata (Mannerheim, 1825)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Tuva, Sayan, Transbaikalia, Russian Far East), Mongolia

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) bipunctata indigiriensis L. Medvedev, 1978

Distribution: Asian Russia (Yakutia)

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) brevipennis Faldermann, 1837

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) chinensis Lefevre, 1887

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, China, Korea

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) crebrecollis L, Medvedev, 1962

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, Korea

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) curtus Lopatin, 1961

Distribution: Kazakhstan Plains, S Uzbekistan, S Tajikistan

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) cyanicornis Germar, 1822

Distribution: SE and southern parts of Central and E Europe, Ciscaucasia, N Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Baikal Area, Tuva, Sayan, Yakutia), Mongolia

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) decipiens Faldermann, 1837

Distribution: Balkans, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Syria, N Iran

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) elegans Lefevre, 1876

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey, N Iran

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) fedtschenkoi Lopatin, 1963

Distribution: Uzbekistan, Tajikistan (Mountains)

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) glasunovi Jacobson, 1893

Distribution: Tajikistan (Mountains), Pamirs

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) humeralis D. H. Schneider, 1792

Distribution: S, Central and the southern part of E Europe, N Kazakhstan, Turkey

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) kaszabi L. Medvedev, 1962

Distribution: Turkey

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) lepida Lefevre, 1872

Distribution: Latvia, Lithuania, Belarus, Ukraine, W European Russia

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) lipskyi Lopatin, 1961

Distribution: Tajikistan

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) longimana longimana (Linnaeus, 1761)

Distribution: W, Central and E Europe, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Altai)

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) longimana dalmatina (Lacordaire, 1848)

Distribution: S Europe, Crimea, Caucasus, Turkey

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) lucida lucida (Germar, 1824)

Distribution: W, Central and western parts of East Europe

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) lucida axillaris (Lacordaire, 1848)

Distribution: Steppe zone of Palaearctic, W Iran

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) maculipennis Lefevre, 1870

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) medvedevi Warchałowski, 1985

Distribution: SE Azerbaijan (Talysh), W Turkmenistan, NW Iran

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) mesopotamica peregrina J. Weise, 1900

Distribution: Daghestan, Transcaucasia, E Turkey

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) metallica metallica Lefevre, 1872

Distribution: SE part of European Russia, Daghestan, W Kazakhstan

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) metallica centrisculpta Pic, 1920

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, SE Tajikistan

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) metallica dzhungarica L. Medvedev, 1980

Distribution: Mongolia, NW China

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) metallica imitatrix L. Medvedev, 1971

Distribution: Asian Russia (Yakutia)

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) metallica mongolica L. Medvedev, 1980

Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva), Mongolia

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) metallica ornatipennis L. Medvedev, 1971

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan (W Tian-Shan)

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) metallica steppensis L. Medvedev, 1971

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai), N and E Kazakhstan

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) oertzeni villosula J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: Transcaucasia, E Turkey

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) ornatus L. Medvedev, 1962

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, (W Tian-Shan)

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) pachysoma L. Medvedev, 1965

Distribution: SE of European Russia, Steppe of Crimea Peninsula, Daghestan, Georgia

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) pallidipennis (Gebler, 1830)

Distribution: S and southern parts of E Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Siberia)

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) propinqua Faldermann, 1837

Distribution: Balkans, Ukraine, Crimea, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) rugicollis Lefevre, 1872

Distribution: Tajikistan, S Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh Mountains), N Iran

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) schneideri J. Weise, 1900

Distribution: Uzbekistan, Tajikistan

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) senicula Kraatz, 1872

Distribution: SE of European Russia, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Mongolia NW China

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) sibirica sibirica (Germar, 1824)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Siberia), N Mongolia, N China

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) sibirica tjutschevi Jacobson, 1900

Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva, Transbaikalia), N Mongolia

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) sibirica transitoria Jacobson 1900

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, S Siberia)

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) stenostoma J. Weise, 1900

Distribution: E. Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, S. Kyrgyzstan

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) subfasciata J. Weise, 1885

Distribution: Azerbaijan, S Turkmenistan, N and W Iran

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) sulcicollis (Lacordaire, 1848)

Distribution: Armenia, Turkey

Labidostomis (Labidostomis) tridentata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (S. Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia, N China

Genus ***Antipus*** DeGeer, 1778

Subgenus ***Antipus (Tituboea)*** Lacordaire, 1848

Antipus (Tituboea) macropus Illiger, 1800

Distribution: S Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Syria, Iran, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan

Antipus (Tituboea) nigriventris Lefevre, 1872

Distribution: S Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Syria, Iran, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan

Antipus (Tituboea) puncticollis L. Medvedev, 1962

Distribution: N Iran, Turkmenistan

Antipus (Tituboea) rugulosa J. Weise, 1898

Distribution: S Transcaucasia

Antipus (Tituboea) silensis J. Weise, 1894

Distribution: Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, S Kazakhstan, E Iran

Genus *Lachnaia* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Lachnaia sexpunctata (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution: W and S Europe, S Ukraine, Turkey

Genus *Clytra* Laicharting, 1781

Subgenus *Clytra (Clytraria)* Semenov, 1903

Clytra (Clytraria) atraphaxidis atraphaxidis (Pallas, 1773)

Distribution: S Europe, the southern part of E Europe, Caucasus, N and E Kazakhstan, Mountains of Central Asia, Turkey, W Iran

Clytra (Clytraria) atraphaxidis asiatica Chujo, 1941

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland), China, Korea

Clytra (Clytraria) atraphaxidis maculifrons Zubkov, 1833

Distribution: SE of European Russia, N and Middle Kazakhstan, Plains of Central Asia, N Iran

Clytra (Clytraria) atraphaxidis punctata J. Weise, 1890

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai), E. Kazakhstan, Mongolia, NW China

Clytra (Clytraria) jacobsoni Semenov, 1903

Distribution: Tajikistan

Clytra (Clytraria) novempunctata Olivier, 1808

Distribution: Balkans, Daghestan, Transcaucasia, Turkey, W Iran, Iraq, Turkmenistan, NE Africa

Clytra (Clytraria) popovi L. Medvedev, 1961

Distribution: Tajikistan

Clytra (Clytraria) rufina (Solsky, 1882)

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Deserts of Central Asia

Clytra (Clytraria) valerianae valerianae Menetries, 1832

Distribution: Balkans, southern E Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, NW Iran

Clytra (Clytraria) valerianae tetrastigma (W. Schmidt, 1841)

Distribution: S Ukraine, Crimea, NW Iran

Subgenus *Clytra (Clytra)* Laicharting, 1781

Clytra (Clytra) arida J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: Asian Russia (W Siberia, Tuva, Sayan, Transbaikalia, Russian Far East), Mongolia, China, Korea

Clytra (Clytra) laeviuscula (Ratzeburg, 1837)

Distribution: Central, S and southern parts of E Europe, Ciscaucasia, Transcaucasia, Turkey, N and E Kazakhstan, E Kyrgyzstan, Afghanistan, N, Tajikistan, NW China

Clytra (Clytra) quadripunctata quadripunctata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, N Iran, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (southern W and Middle Siberia, Amurland)

Clytra (Clytra) quadripunctata appendicina (Lacordaire, 1848)

Distribution: Southern part of Central and W Europe, Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Clytra (Clytra) quadripunctata turfanica Lopatin, 1962

Distribution: China (Turfan)

Genus *Smaragdina* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Subgenus *Smaragdina (Calyptorhina)* Lacordaire, 1848

Smaragdina (Calyptorhina) aeneoviridis Lopatin, 1975

Distribution: S Tajikistan

Smaragdina (Calyptorhina) biornata Lefevre, 1872

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey, W Iran

Smaragdina (Calyptorhina) chloris caucasica L. Medvedev, 1971

Distribution: SW Ciscaucasia, Abkhazia

Smaragdina (Calyptorhina) golda Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Amurland Maritime Prov.), Korea, Japan

Smaragdina (Calyptorhina) limbata (Steven, 1806)

Distribution: Balkans, Romania, Hungary, E Ciscaucasia, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East

Smaragdina (Calyptorhina) unipunctata (Olivier, 1808)

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey, Middle East, Turkmenistan

Smaragdina (Calyptorhina) viridis viridis (Kraatz, 1882)

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Turkey

Smaragdina (Calyptorhina) viridis comans (Jacobson, 1925)

Distribution: SE Azerbaijan, Turkmenistan, N Iran

Subgenus *Smaragdina (Nanosmaragdina)* Lopatin et Kulenova, 1985

Smaragdina (Nanosmaragdina) macilenta (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Chu-Ili Mountains), Uzbekistan, W Tajikistan

Subgenus *Smaragdina (Monrosiana)* L. Medvedev, 1992

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) affinis (Illiger, 1794)

Distribution: S, Central and E Europe, Turkey, N Africa

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) aurita aurita (Linnaeus, 1767)

Distribution: Europe except for the North, Turkey

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) aurita auritoides Achard, 1923

Distribution: Caucasus, NW Iran, NE Turkey

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) aurita hammarstroemi (Jacobson, 1901)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) aurita nigrocyanea (Motschulsky, 1866)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Japan

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) collaris collaris (Fabricius, 1781)

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Tuva, E Siberia), Mongolia, China

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) collaris lateralis Gebler, 1848

Distribution: E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Altai, Transbaikalia, Yakutia)

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) discolor discolor (Solsky, 1881)

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) discolor rufilabris (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Chu-Ili Mountains)

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) discolor viridiceps (J. Weise, 1892)

Distribution: Mountains of the SE Kazakhstan and Central Asia (except for the Turkmenistan)

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) flavicollis (Charpentier, 1825)

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North and South, Turkey, Algeria

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) hypocrita (Lacordaire, 1848)

Distribution: Serbia, Bulgaria, Ukraine (S Crimea), Caucasus, Turkey

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) labilis sahlbergi (Jacobson, 1901)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, Korea

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) obscuripes (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Maritime Prov.), N China

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) potanini L. Medvedev, 1970

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.), China

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) punctatissima J. Weise, 1892

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) salicina (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (W Siberia), Caucasus, Turkey, E Kazakhstan

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) semiauratiaca Fairmaire, 1888

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Amurland, S Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) stenroosi (Jacobson, 1901)

Distribution: S. Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) thoracica thoracica Fischer-Waldheim, 1842

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Siberia), Mountains of Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, SE Kazakhstan

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) thoracica dzhungarica L. Medvedev, 1980

Distribution: NW China

Smaragdina (Monrosiana) xanthaspis (Germar, 1824)

Distribution: SE and southern parts of Central Europe, Transcaucasia, Turkey

Genus ***Cheilotoma*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Subgenus ***Cheilotoma (Cheilotoma)*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Cheilotoma (Cheilotoma) erythrostoma (Faldermann, 1837)

Distribution: SE Europe, NW Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Iran

Cheilotoma (Cheilotoma) musciformis (Goeze, 1777)

Distribution: S Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (southern parts of W and Middle Siberia, Transbaikalia)

Subgenus *Cheilotoma (Exaesiognatha)* Jacobson, 1923

Cheilotoma (Exaesiognatha) ivanovi Jacobson, 1923

Distribution: Plains of Central Asia from W Turkmenistan to Fergana Valley and S Tajikistan

Genus *Coptocephala* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Subgenus *Coptocephala (Coptocephala)* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Coptocephala (Coptocephala) chalybaea chalybaea (Germar, 1824)

Distribution: SE Europe, NW and Minor Caucasus, Daghestan

Coptocephala (Coptocephala) chalybaea apicalis Lacordaire, 1848

Distribution: Steppe zone from S Ukraine and Crimea to Central Kazakhstan, Ciscaucasia

Coptocephala (Coptocephala) gebleri Gebler, 1841

Distribution: SE Balkan, S Ukraine (Crimea) and European Russia, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Asian Russia (southern parts of W Siberia, Altai)

Coptocephala (Coptocephala) hissarica Lopatin, 1963

Distribution: SE Uzbekistan, W Tajikistan

Coptocephala (Coptocephala) orientalis Baly, 1873

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia. Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, China, Japan

Coptocephala (Coptocephala) rubicunda rubicunda (Laicharting, 1781)

Distribution: SW, Central and southern E Europe, Ciscaucasia, Georgia, N Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (southern parts of W and Middle Siberia, Cisbaikalia)

Coptocephala (Coptocephala) unifasciata unifasciata (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Syria, E Kazakhstan, W Pamirs, Asian Russia (southern parts of W Siberia)

Coptocephala (Coptocephala) unifasciata australis L. Medvedev, 1965

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Central Asia (Tian-Shan and Hissar-Darvaz Mountains)

Coptocephala (Coptocephala) unifasciata deserta L. Medvedev, 1965

Distribution: Desert and semi-desert areas of Kazakhstan and Central Asia

Coptocephala (Coptocephala) unifasciata destinoi Fairmaire, 1884
Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East

Subfamily ***Criocerinae*** Latreille, 1807

Tribe ***Criocerini*** Latreille, 1807

Genus ***Lilioceris*** Rietter, 1912

Lilioceris lilii (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution: Europe except for the North, SE Kazakhstan (Dzhungar Alatau), Asian Russia (W and Middle Siberia, Amurland), N Africa

Lilioceris merdigera (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for the extreme North, S and Central Asia, N America

Lilioceris ruficoillis (Baly, 1865)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S. Maritime Prov.), China, Korea

Lilioceris rugata (Baly, 1865)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Lilioceris scapularis (Baly, 1859)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Genus ***Crioceris*** Geoffroy, 1762

Crioceris asparagi (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for the North, Mediterranean (except for Apennines Peninsula, Sicily, Corsica, Sardinia, Crete), Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkmenistan, introduced to N America and Argentina

Crioceris bicrucata (C. R. Sahlberg, 1823)

Distribution: SE European Russia (Volgograd Distr.), Caucasus, Greece, Turkey, Central Asia

Crioceris duodecimpunctata duodecimpunctata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: All over the Palaearctic except the North

Crioceris duodecimpunctata hypopsila Jacobson, 1907

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Crioceris duodecimpunctata orientalis (Jacoby, 1885)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Khabarovsk Prov., Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Crioceris iliensis J. Weise, 1900

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan

Crioceris oshanini Dohrn, 1884

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Crioceris quatuordecimpunctata quatuordecimpunctata (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution: Central and SE Europe

Crioceris quatuordecimpunctata sibirica J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Khabarovsk Prov., Maritime Prov.), NE China, Korea, Japan

Crioceris quinquepunctata (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution: Mountains of Central and East Europe, Dinars Mts, S Belarus, Ukraine, S European Russia

Tribe *Lemiini* Gyllenhal, 1813

Genus *Oulema* Des Gozis, 1886

Oulema dilutipes (Fairmaire, 1885)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Oulema duftschmidi (L. Redtenbacher, 1874)

Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Oulema erichsonii (Suffrian, 1841)

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North and South, Asian Russia (Siberia, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, Japan

Oulema gallaeciana (Heyden, 1870)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for the Kazakhstan and Central Asia

Oulema melanopus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia, east to Mongolia)

Oulema oryzae (Kuwayama, 1929)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), China, Japan

Oulema pygmaea Kraatz, 1879

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Khabarovsk Prov. Maritime Prov.), China, Korea

Oulema septentrionis J. Weise, 1880

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North and South

Oulema tristis (Herbst, 1786)

Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (S. Siberia, Amurland), Kazakhstan, Korea, Japan

Genus ***Lema*** Fabricius, 1798

Subgenus ***Lema (Lema)*** Fabricius, 1798

Lema (Lema) cyanella (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for the Central Asia

Lema (Lema) diversa Baly, 1873

Distribution: Asian Russia (S. Maritime Prov.), Korea, China, Japan

Lema (Lema) scutellaris (Kraatz, 1879)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Korea, China, Japan

Subgenus ***Lema (Microlema)*** Pic, 1932

Lema (Microlema) decempunctata Gebler, 1830

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, N China, Japan, Kazakhstan

Lema (Microlema) quadrimaculata Gebler, 1845

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan

Subfamily ***Donaciinae*** Kirby, 1837

Tribe ***Donaciini*** Kirby, 1837

Genus ***Donacia*** Fabricius, 1775

Subgenus ***Donacia (Donacia)*** Fabricius, 1775

Donacia (Donacia) aequidorsis Jacobson, 1894

Distribution: SE European Russia, W Kazakhstan

Donacia (Donacia) antiqua Kunze, 1818

Distribution: N, Central and Northern part of E. Europe

Donacia (Donacia) bactriana bactriana J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: S. Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Donacia (Donacia) bactriana sahlbergi Jacobson, 1901

Distribution: Central Asia

Donacia (Donacia) breviscula Jacobson, 1899

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland)

Donacia (Donacia) crassipes Fabricius, 1775

Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Siberia east to Baikal)

Donacia (Donacia) fedtschenkoae Jacobson, 1899

Distribution: Uzbekistan

Donacia (Donacia) flemola Goecke, 1944

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea

Donacia (Donacia) gracilicornis Jacobson, 1892

Distribution: Transcaucasia, W. Iran

Donacia (Donacia) kirgizkaisaka Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: Siberia (Irtysh River)

Donacia (Donacia) knipovitschi Jacobson, 1927

Distribution: Asian Russia (S. Maritime Prov.), NE China

Donacia (Donacia) koenigi Jacobson, 1899

Distribution: Transcaucasia

Donacia (Donacia) kraatzi J. Weise, 1882

Distribution: Armenia, N. Turkey

Donacia (Donacia) mistschenkoi Jacobson, 1910

Distribution: Caucasus

Donacia (Donacia) ochroleuca J. Weise, 1882

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China

Donacia (Donacia) polita Kunze, 1818

Distribution: S. Europe, Moldavia

Donacia (Donacia) ussuriensis L. Medvedev, 1973

Distribution: Asian Russia (S. Maritime Prov.)

Subgenus *Donacia (Donaciella)* Reitter, 1920

Donacia (Donaciella) cinerea Herbst, 1784

Distribution: Europe, Transcaucasia, Kazakhstan, W. Siberia

Donacia (Donaciella) clavipes clavipes Fabricius, 1793

Distribution: All over the Palaearctic except for the extreme North

Donacia (Donaciella) clavipes glabrata Solsky, 1872

Distribution: Asian Russia (E. Siberia, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia

Donacia (Donaciella) tomentosa Ahrens, 1810

Distribution: N and Central Europe, Azerbaijan, E. Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Asian Russia (S. Siberia, Altai)

Subgenus ***Donacia (Donaciomima)*** L. Medvedev, 1973

Donacia (Donaciomima) aquatica (Linnaeus), 1758

Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (Siberia), N China, Japan

Donacia (Donaciomima) bicolora bicolora Zschach, 1788

Distribution: Europe except for the South, Asian Russia (W Siberia), Central Asia

Donacia (Donaciomima) brevicornis Ahrens, 1810

Distribution: N. and NE Europe

Donacia (Donaciomima) brevitarsis C. G. Thomson, 1884

Distribution: N and NE Europe, Alps

Donacia (Donaciomima) clavareani Jacobson, 1906

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), China, Japan

Donacia (Donaciomima) dentata Hoppe, 1795

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia)

Donacia (Donaciomima) fennica (Paykull, 1800)

Distribution: N. northeast of Central and E. Europe, Asian Russia

Donacia (Donaciomima) impressa Paykull, 1799

Distribution: Europe except for the outermost North and South, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia

Donacia (Donaciomima) malinovskiyi Ahrens, 1810

Distribution: Central and E Europe, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W Siberia)

Donacia (Donaciomima) marginata marginata Hoppe, 1795

Distribution: Europe except for the North, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Asian Russia (W Siberia)

Donacia (Donaciomima) obscura obscura Gyllenhal, 1813

Distribution: Europe except for the Mediterranean

Donacia (Donaciomima) obscura splendens Jacobson, 1894

Distribution: Asian Russia (W and Middle Siberia, Altais, Transbaikalia, Yakutia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.)

Donacia (Donaciomima) semicuprea Panzer, 1796

Distribution: W and Central Europe, Asian Russia (Siberia east to Baikal)

Donacia (Donaciomima) simplex Fabricius, 1775

Distribution: W and Central Europe, Asian Russia (S. Siberia, Transbaikalia), Mongolia

Donacia (Donaciomima) sparganii sparganii Ahrens, 1810

Distribution: N, Central and E. Europe, Asian Russia (W. Siberia)

Donacia (Donaciomima) sparganii gracilipes Jacoby, 1885

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, NE Siberia, Kamchatka, Amurland, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Japan

Donacia (Donaciomima) thalassina intermedia Jacobson, 1899

Distribution: Asian Russia (Siberia, Maritime Prov.) Mongolia

Donacia (Donaciomima) thalassina thalassina Germar, 1811

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North, Asian Russia (S. Siberia, Transbaikalia, Tuva), Mongolia

Donacia (Donaciomima) versicolore (Brahm, 1790)

Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (SW Siberia)

Donacia (Donaciomima) vulgaris issykensis Jacobson, 1900

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Donacia (Donaciomima) vulgaris vulgaris Zschach, 1788

Distribution: All over the Palaearctic

Subgenus ***Donacia (Cyphogaster)*** Goecke, 1934

Donacia (Cyphogaster) lenzi Schonfeldt, 1888

Distribution: Asian Russia (S. Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Donacia (Cyphogaster) provosti Fairmaire, 1885

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Genus ***Sominella*** Jacobson, 1908

Sominella macrocnemia (Fischer-Waldheim, 1823)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Yakutia, Khabarovsk Prov. Maritime Prov.), China

Tribe ***Haemoniini*** Chen, 1941

Genus ***Macroplea*** Samouelle, 1819

Macroplea appendiculata (Panzer, 1794)

Distribution: Europe except for the North and South, W Siberia

Macroplea mutica mutica (Fabricius, 1792)

Distribution: Coastal parts of the North, White, Baltic, Mediterranean, Black and Caspian Sea

Macroplea mutica japana (Jacoby, 1885)

Distribution: Asian Russia (E. Siberia), Japan

Genus ***Neohaemonia*** Szekessy, 1941

Neohaemonia voronovae L. Medvedev, 1977

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia), Mongolia

Tribe ***Plateumarini*** Askevold, 1990

Genus ***Plateumaris*** C. G. Thomson, 1866

Plateumaris amurensis J. Weise, 1898

Distribution: Asian Russia (Yakutia, Amurland, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Japan

Plateumaris braccata (Scopoli, 1772)

Distribution: Europe except for the North and South, Caucasus, SE Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia)

Plateumaris consimilis consimilis (Schrank, 1781)

Distribution: Europe except for the North and South, Urals, Asian Russia (Siberia)

Plateumaris consimilis orientalis Shavrov, 1948

Distribution: Asian Russia (S. Maritime Prov.)

Plateumaris constricticollis kurilensis L. Medvedev, 1978

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Kurile Is., Kunashir)

Plateumaris obsoleta Jacobson, 1894

Distribution: Asian Russia (S. Maritime Prov.)

Plateumaris roscida J. Weise, 1912

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Yakutia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.)

Plateumaris rustica (Kunze, 1818)

Distribution: Europe except for the South, Asian Russia (W. Siberia), N. Algeria

Plateumaris sachalinensis L. Medvedev, 1973

Distribution: Asian Russia (S. Sakhalin)

Plateumaris sericea sericea (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for the South, W and Central Siberia

Plateumaris sericea caucasica Zaitzev, 1930

Distribution: NW Caucasus (Teberda, Bakuriani)

Plateumaris sericea sibirica (Solsky, 1872)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Siberia, Amurland, Maritime Prov., Kamchatka, Sakhalin), Mongolia, China, Japan

Plateumaris wisei Duvivier, 1885

Distribution: N and C Europe, Asian Russia (W. Siberia, Tuva, Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin), Mongolia, Japan

Subfamily ***Eumolpinae*** Hope, 1840

Tribe ***Nodinini*** Chen, 1940

Genus ***Basilepta*** Baly, 1860

Basilepta balyi (Harold, 1877)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Japan

Basilepta fulvipes (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov., Kurile Is.), Mongolia, Korea, China, Japan

Basilepta kaszabi Lopatin, 1962

Distribution: China (Timbu)

Genus ***Weiselina*** Reitter, 1890

Weiselina lenkorana Reitter, 1890

Distribution: E Azerbaijan

Genus *Pagria* Lefevre, 1884

Pagria signata (Motschulsky, 1858)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), Korea, China, S Asia

Genus *Bedelia* Lefevre, 1875

Bedelia angustata Lefevre, 1875

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Iran

Bedelia kaschgarica Lopatin, 1962

Distribution: NW China (Kaschgar)

Bedelia kokanica (Solsky, 1882)

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan

Bedelia viridicoerulea Reitter, 1901

Distribution: Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan

Genus *Chloropterus* Morawitz, 1861

Chloropterus grandis J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan Mongolia

Chloropterus lefevrei Reitter, 1890

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Valleys of Kazakhstan and Central Asia, Near East

Chloropterus unguiculatus Lopatin, 1965

Distribution: S Tajikistan

Chloropterus versicolor (Morawitz, 1860)

Distribution: Southern parts of Steppe zone of Ukraine and European Russia, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, SW Turkmenistan

Genus *Cleoporus* Lefevre, 1884

Cleoporus variabilis (Baly, 1874)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Tribe *Colasposomini* Springlova, 1960

Genus *Colasposoma* Laporte, 1833

Colasposoma dauricum Mannerheim, 1849

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin), Mongolia, N China, Korea

Tribe *Eumolpini* Jacoby, 1908

Genus *Eumolpus* Illiger, 1798

Eumolpus asclepiadeus (Pallas, 1773)

Distribution: W, S, Central, and southern parts of E Europe, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Southern part of W Siberia)

Eumolpus chinensis Baly, 1859

Distribution: Mongolia, Central and E China

Eumolpus globicollis Lefevre, 1888

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Korea, N China

Eumolpus goniostoma J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia), Mongolia, N China

Genus *Abiromorphus* Pic, 1924

Abiromorphus anceyi Pic, 1924

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.) NE China Korea

Genus *Chrysochares* Morawitz, 1861

Chrysochares asiaticus asiaticus (Pallas, 1771)

Distribution: S of European Russia, Transcaucasia

Chrysochares asiaticus orientalis Lopatin, 1963

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, S Tajikistan

Chrysochares constricticollis Lopatin, 1963

Distribution: E Georgia, Daghestan

Chrysochares punctatus (Gebler, 1845)

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, S and N Tajikistan, Mongolia, NW China

Tribe *Adoxini* Jacoby, 1908

Genus *Malegia* Lefevre, 1883

Malegia aenea (Chen, 1940)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland Maritime Prov.), Korea, N China

Malegia colchica Reitter, 1912

Distribution: Caucasus (Georgia)

Malegia jacobsoni Sumakov, 1901

Distribution: S Turkmenistan

Malegia turkestanica turkestanica Reitter, 1890

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan

Malegia turkestanica uralensis Reitter, 1912

Distribution: NW Kazakhstan

Genus *Lypesthes* Baly, 1863

Lypesthes ater (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), Korea, China

Genus *Andosia* J. Weise, 1896

Andosia reitteri J. Weise, 1896

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, S Tajikistan

Genus *Caspiana* Lopatin, 1977

Caspiana armata Lopatin, 1977

Distribution: SW Turkmenistan

Genus *Parnops* Jacobson, 1894

Parnops glasunovi ferghanus Lopatin, 1976

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Foothill Plains of Chatkal Mountain Range)

Parnops glasunovi glasunovi Jacobson, 1894

Distribution: S Turkmenistan, Iran, Uzbekistan, S Tajikistan

Genus *Trichochrysea* Baly 1861

Trichochrysea amygdali amygdali (Ogloblin, 1941)

Distribution: Tajikistan (Hissar, Babatagh, Gazimailik Mountain Ranges)

Trichochrysea amygdali nuratavica Lopatin, 1976

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Nuratau Mountain Range)

Trichochrysea arnoldii (L. Medvedev, 1957)

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Fergan, Baubash-Ata, Bozbutau Mountain Ranges)

Trichochrysea occidentalis (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan (W Tian-Shan)

Genus *Dermestops* Jacobson, 1898

Dermestops ahngeri Jacobson, 1898

Distribution: Turkmenistan

Genus *Callipta* Lefevre, 1885

Callipta borealis Lopatin, 1876

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Kara-Kum Desert, Bukantau, Tamdytau, Aktau Mountains)

Callipta fausti fausti (J. Weise, 1882)

Distribution: E Transcaucasia (Azerbaijan, S Daghestan)

Callipta fausti badghyza Lopatin, 1997

Distribution: Turkmenistan (Badkhyz)

Callipta fausti balchana Lopatin, 1997

Distribution: W Turkmenistan, (Balkhan Mountains)

Callipta fausti murgabica Lopatin, 1997

Distribution: Turkmenistan

Callipta fausti palvanica Lopatin, 1997

Distribution: Turkmenistan (Kaplanhyr Plateau)

Callipta fausti turcomana L. Medvedev, 1957

Distribution: S Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh Mountain Range)

Genus *Aphilenia* J. Weise, 1889

Subgenus *Aphilenia (Pseudoaphilenia)* Lopatin, 1976

Aphilenia (Pseudoaphilenia) hauseri J. Weise, 1894

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Sandy Deserts), S Central Asia (Sandy Deserts)

Subgenus *Aphilenia (Aphilenia)* J. Weise, 1889

Aphilenia (Aphilenia) interrupta J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, SW Tajikistan (Sandy Deserts)

Aphilenia (Aphilenia) ornata Reitter, 1888

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan (Deserts)

Aphilenia (Aphilenia) parvula J. Weise, 1894

Distribution: Turkemenistan, Uzbekistan (Deserts)

Genus *Atomyria* Jacobson, 1894

Atomyria sarafschanica (Solsky, 1882)

Distribution: SW Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan (Bank of the Rivers Amu-Darya, Piandzh, Vakhsh)

Genus *Macrocoma* Chapuis, 1874

Macrocoma rubripes turcmena Lopatin, 1976

Distribution: S Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh Mountain Range)

Macrocoma sarvadensis (Solsky, 1882)

Distribution: Kazakhstan and Central Asia

Genus *Bromius* Chevrolat et Dejean, 1837

Bromius obscurus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North, Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East), Japan, Introduced to N America

Genus *Anidania* Reitter, 1889

Anidania luctuosa (Solsky, 1882)

Distribution: S.Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, N Afghanistan

Genus *Adoxinia* Reitter, 1888

Adoxinia spinipes Reitter, 1888

Distribution: Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, W Tajikistan (Sandy Deserts)

Genus *Pachnephoptrus* Reitter, 1892

Pachnephoptrus weisei Reitter, 1892

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Afghanistan

Genus *Pachnephorus* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Subgenus *Pachnephorus (Pachnephoriscus)* Lopatin, 1976

Pachnephorus (Pachnephoriscus) jacobsoni Lopatin, 1976

Distribution: Uzbekistan

Subgenus *Pachnephorus (Pachnephorus)* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Pachnephorus (Pachnephorus) brunneus L. Medvedev, 1957

Distribution: Turkmenistan

Pachnephorus (Pachnephorus) canus J. Weise, 1882

Distribution: S Ukraine, Daghestan, E Mediterranean

Pachnephorus (Pachnephorus) fulvus Lopatin, 1976

Distribution: Uzbekistan

Pachnephorus (Pachnephorus) lewisi Baly, 1878

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), China

Pachnephorus (Pachnephorus) pilosus (Rossi, 1790)

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North, Caucasus, Turkey, Siberia

Pachnephorus (Pachnephorus) tessellatus (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: All over the Palaearctic

Pachnephorus (Pachnephorus) turcomanicus L. Medvedev, 1957

Distribution: Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan

Pachnephorus (Pachnephorus) villosus (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: S and SE Europe, Crimea, Turkey, Caucasus

Subfamily *Hispinae* Gyllenhal, 1813

Genus *Dactylispa* J. Weise, 1897

Dactylispa angulosa (Solsky, 1871)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Dactylispa excisa (Kraatz, 1879)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea

Dactylispa marginicollis borealis L. Medvedev, 1963

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.)

Dactylispa masonii Gestro, 1923

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov., Sakhalin), China, Japan

Genus *Rhadinosa* J. Weise, 1905

Rhadinosa nigorcyanea (Motschulsky, 1861)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Genus *Hispa* Linnaeus, 1767

Hispa atra Linnaeus, 1767

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (S Siberia)

Genus *Hispellinus* J. Weise 1897

Hispellinus moerens (Baly, 1874)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Amurland), China, Japan

Genus *Acmenychus* J. Weise, 1905

Acmenychus caucasicus (Heyden, 1878)

Distribution: Transcaucasia

Acmenychus inermis (Zubkov, 1833)

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Central Asia, NE China, Mongolia

Genus *Cassidispa* Gestro, 1899

Cassidispa relictata L. Medvedev, 1957

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.)

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